

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

SensRes

Sensor data for downscaling digital soil maps to higher resolutions

Deliverables WP3.4; WP4.3; WP5.4; WP6.2
Submitted manuscript

Due date of deliverable: M54 (July 2024)

Actual submission date: M58 (November 2024)

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695
Project acronym: EJP SOIL
Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils
Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu
Project title:
Project website:

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020
Project duration: 60 months
Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1
Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: D#WP3.4; WP4.3; WP5.4; WP6.2
DELIVERABLE TITLE: An open framework for downscaling soil
maps using sensor data: Five case studies
across diverse European landscapes
DELIVERABLE TYPE : Manuscript
WORK PACKAGE N: WP3,WP4,WP5 and WP6
WORK PACKAGE NAME:
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14717728](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717728)
LICENSE: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
International
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**An open framework for downscaling soil maps using sensor data: Five case studies
across diverse European landscapes**

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Keywords: Downscaling; soil organic carbon; high-resolution maps; soil management; satellite; fusion data

Abstract

Sustainable soil management is recognized as a pivotal solution for addressing current and future global challenges, but existing global and national soil maps often lack the fine-scale resolution required for local or intra-field assessments. Here, we aimed to develop an open access framework to downscale soil maps using remote and proximal sensor data and test it for predicting soil organic carbon (SOC) and clay across different regions of Europe. To facilitate the dissemination of this framework, we developed the R package “*soilscaler*”, which contains integrated functions for producing downscaled soil maps. This approach uses coarse resolution map as a baseline, incorporating sensor data and soil observations to train a model explaining local variation of soil properties. We tested the framework in Denmark, Northern Ireland, Lithuania, The Netherlands and Turkey. For comparison, we also we also created high-resolution maps using a conventional digital soil mapping (DSM) approach for each field independently. We found that the downscaling performance depends on the quality of the coarse-resolution soil maps, the spatial variability of soil properties within a given field, and the range of inter-field variations in each country. Although the downscaling process showed lower performance than the conventional DSM approach, the results indicate that the downscaled maps better represent local variability than existing national and global soil maps. Additionally, we found that remote sensing sensors generally better represent the spatial distribution of SOC, while proximal soil sensors better capture clay contents. Future studies should focus on gathering more sensor data and correlating it with soil properties to improve predictions based solely on sensor data.

1. Introduction

Sustainable soil management is recognized as a pivotal solution for addressing current and future global challenges, including climate change adaptation, water quality improvement, and food security (Montanarella & Panos, 2021; Adhikari & Hartemink, 2016). Effective soil management depends critically on detailed knowledge of soil physical, chemical and biological properties, not only at a single sample level but across spatial scales that capture field-level variability (Futa et al., 2024). However, existing global and national soil maps often lack the fine-scale resolution required for local or intra-field assessments (Poggio et al., 2021; Arrouays et al., 2014), which is essential for farm-level management decisions, such as precision fertilization, irrigation scheduling, or crop selection. Local digital soil mapping is an optimal way to address intra-field soil variability, but it requires a comprehensive soil sampling design which is time-consuming and costly to be done in multiple fields. To bridge this gap across different scales, recent efforts have focused on downscaling soil maps to achieve higher resolutions (Malone et al., 2012; Odgers et al., 2014; Roudier et al., 2017; Gagkas & Lilly, 2019; Møller et al., 2019). These studies typically employ virtual samples generated from coarse-resolution maps along with high-resolution environmental covariates to improve map precision. While effective, this approach is limited by its inability to integrate sensor-based data that may only be locally accessible, such as electromagnetic induction (EMI) or bare soil imagery, which can provide more accurate, localized information.

Remote and proximal sensing technologies are increasingly used to capture soil variation through indirect measures of soil physical and chemical properties (Doolittle & Brevik, 2014; Beamish & Klinck, 2013; Ma and Minasny, 2023). These technologies hold potential as proxies for creating high-resolution soil maps that enhance local sustainable soil management strategies (Mulder et al., 2011). Remote sensing, for instance, has been intensively used in mapping various soil properties at local scales (Ge et al., 2011). The increase of open-

access satellite imagery (e.g., Landsat and Sentinel-2) has enabled researchers globally to explore and refine techniques for soil mapping, especially using bare soil images that reveal variations in soil organic matter and moisture content based on spectral responses (Yuzugullu et al., 2024; Zeyliger et al., 2022). High-resolution satellite and hyperspectral images offer even more potential by providing deeper insights into soil variability, though data availability, cloud and vegetation cover, and the cost of commercial satellite imagery remain constraints (Gomez et al., 2008). As an alternative, UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) imagery is becoming increasingly accessible, providing high-resolution data for soil surface characterization that has become instrumental for field-level soil management (Yan et al., 2023; Argento et al., 2021). However, both satellite and UAV sensors primarily capture surface characteristics and have little or no capacity for assessing sub-surface soil properties.

Subsoil characteristics can be evaluated using proximal sensors (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2010; 2011). Electromagnetic induction (EMI) sensors, for instance, are widely applied to map soil moisture, texture variations and salinity (Doolittle & Brevik, 2014; O'Leary et al., 2024; Koganti et al., 2018). Gamma-ray sensors also have been applied to assess soil properties such as texture and organic matter content by detecting natural radiation differences across soil layers (Beamish & Klinck, 2013; Wilford, 2012; Koganti et al., 2023). Despite the promise of remote and proximal sensing technologies for local soil mapping, conventional soil survey methodologies at the farm level still rely on high-density sampling, which can be both costly and time-consuming. Furthermore, most sensor-based methods still rely on local samples for calibration, which increases the time and resources needed to map new locations. Recently, Møller et al. (2021) combined remote and proximal sensing data to downscale soil maps. However, this method was applied only to fields in Denmark, and further research is needed to understand the effectiveness of different sensors in varied contexts.

In this study, we aim to further develop and test this downscaling approach by creating an R package with streamlined functions for generating high-resolution soil maps, applicable across different regions in Europe, representing contrasting soil and climatic conditions. Our specific objectives are to (i) develop an R package for implementing the downscaling method; (ii) evaluate the individual contributions of satellite imagery, UAV data, and proximal sensors for downscaling soil maps; and (iii) investigate sensor fusion techniques for optimizing high-resolution soil mapping in diverse European landscapes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. *Soilscaler* R package

We developed a downscaling approach and, to facilitate its dissemination and implementation, we organized the framework into an R package with integrated functions for producing the downscaled maps. The *soilscaler* R package is available online (<https://github.com/anbm-dk/soilscaler/tree/main>) and contains the Danish fields and input datasets for testing the framework. The aim of the *soilscaler* R package is to facilitate the use of sensor technologies to downscale coarse-resolution regional soil maps to higher-resolution maps that can be applied at the field or farm level. The package provides a set of functions, which should be easy to implement, while allowing flexibility for experimentation. In the default setup, the main function *make_downscaler* requires an input soil map (Coarse-resolution map) as well as sensor measurements and soil observations from at least three sites (fields). By default, the function uses the input map as a baseline for the target soil property. It then uses the sensor data and soil observations to train a model explaining the local variation of the soil property and adds this trend to the baseline.

The function automatically tests the accuracy of predictions at new locations by means of cross-validation between the sites. The user can select the method to predict local variations

from a range of statistical model types available in the caret R package (Linear model, Random Forest, etc). Additional features also include options to scale observations and/or sensor measurements and to use the input map as an additional covariate. The user can even omit the use of an input map, although this option will disable some features of the package. In our case, we selected the Random Forest method, and the Lins Concordance Coefficient Correlation (CCC), RMSE and NULL_RMSE (Null model) to measure the performance of the models.

2.2. Study sites and soil sampling

We applied the downscaling approach in five case studies: Denmark, Lithuania, Northern Ireland (UK), Turkey and The Netherlands (Fig. 1). In all case studies, we selected from 4 to 5 fields, where we collected soil samples and analysed for soil organic carbon and clay content (Table 1).

Figure 1. Five case studies used to test the downscaling framework “soilscaler” across Europe.

Table 1: Size and number of samples for each field used in the downscaling in the different study cases.

Country	Site name	Field size (ha)	Samples (n)
Denmark	<i>Estrup</i>	1.3	45
	<i>Faarstrup</i>	2.4	93
	<i>Jyndevad</i>	2.4	88
	<i>Silstrup</i>	1.7	60
	<i>Vindum</i>	11.7	285
Lithuania	<i>Vėžaičiai</i>	2.3	58
	<i>Lyduokiai</i>	4.7	112
	<i>Rumokai</i>	2.8	80
	<i>Vievininkai</i>	2.7	70
Northern Ireland	<i>Barn</i>	1.0	7
	<i>Hill</i>	3.0	21
	<i>Brecart_A</i>	5.3	38
	<i>Brecart_B</i>	1.8	14
Netherlands	<i>PlassteegNoord</i>	3.5	26
	<i>PlassteegZuid1</i>	1.8	12
	<i>PlassteegZuid2</i>	1.9	12
Turkey	<i>Karapınar</i>	4.0	80
	<i>Cihanbeyli</i>	4.0	80
	<i>Karatay</i>	4.0	80
	<i>Kadinhani</i>	4.0	80

In Denmark, the five fields (Estrup, Faarstrup, Jyndevad, Silstrup, and Vindum) covered different soil types and landscapes features. Estrup has a slightly sloping clay till and glaciofluvial sand surface, with soils classified as Luvic Stagnic Chernic Phaeozems and Umbrisols. Faarstrup is characterized by clay and sand till with Cambic Stagnic Chernic Phaeozems, sloping westward. Jyndevad lies on a glacial outwash plain dominated by Umbric Podzols and glaciofluvial sand. Silstrup has clay till soils (Cambic Luvic Chernic Phaeozems) and a steeper northern slope. Vindum, the largest field, has an undulating terrain with clay till, glaciofluvial sand, and peat, along with various soils including Umbrisols, Phaeozems, Luvisols and Histosols.

In Lithuania, we sampled four fields reflecting diverse agro-ecological conditions. The Vėžaičiai field is located in the Southwestern Samogitian moraine plain, with soil types Glossic Albic Eutric Retisol (Loamic, Aric, Drainic) and Epigleyic Albic Haplic Luvisol (Loamic, Aric), and a cool, wet climate, with crops rotate under conventional practices. Lyduokiai is managed managed with no-till practices, lies on the Western Aukštaitija upland and has soil types Epigleyic Epicalcaric Luvisol (Loamic, Humic), Endogleyic Epicalcaric Luvisol (Loamic, Humic) Eutric Planosol (Loamic, Drainic) within a cold, moderately wet zone. Rumokai is located in the Lower Nemunas limnoglacial plain, has soil types Endocalcaric Gleysol (Siltic, Aric, Drainic, Humic) and Epigleyic Endocalcaric Cambisol (Siltic, Aric, Drainic, Humic) suitable for sugar beet and cereals, under conventional practices. Vievininkai is a hilly field in southeastern Lithuania, features moderately acidic soil (Endocalcaric Haplic Luvisol (Loamic, eroded) and is used mainly for potato and cereal crops, and falls within a moderately cool, wet agro-climatic zone (Nemoral Environmental Zone) .

Four fields were sampled in Northern Ireland, UK (Barn, Hill, Brecart_A and Brecart_B). Barn and Hill are located at the AFBI research station at Crossnacreevy, Belfast. The soil at Crossnacreevy is clay loam, and the fields were in a cereal-grass rotation. Brecart A and Brecart B are located at Toomebridge, County Antrim and both fields have been in spring barley – grass silage rotation since 2021, and have a ground water gley, and silt loam soil. The fields are located in the Atlantic North Environmental Zone (Metzger et al. 2005), and the climate is temperate and maritime.

In The Netherlands, we used three fields for the downscaling approach located in the Lusitanian environmental zone with a sandy soil texture. In Turkey, we used four fields (Karapınar, Cihanbeyli, Kadinhani, and Karatay) located in the middle of the country. Karapınar is located at 1026 m above sea level and has a flat landscape with a mean annual temperature of 10.9 °C and annual precipitation of 279.5 mm. Cihanbeyli is located 1125 m

above sea level, with mean annual temperature of 10.8 °C, and annual precipitation of 438.4 mm. Kadinhani is located at 966 m above sea level, with mean annual temperature of 12.3 °C, and annual precipitation of 322.5 mm. Karatay is also located at 1026 m above sea level, with a mean annual temperature of 13.5 °C and annual precipitation of 323.8 mm.

2.3. Coarse resolution maps

Coarse-resolution maps at global and national scales were used as input maps for the downscaling process. Due to different conditions within each country, we developed four different scenarios based on the inclusion or exclusion of coarse-resolution maps as input for the downscaling process.

SoilGrids: In this scenario, we used the coarse-resolution maps of SOC and clay from SoilGrids map layers (Poggio et al., 2021), which have a resolution of 250m. We tested the use of SoilGrids layers for all study sites.

Soilscaler: In this scenario, we used national SOC and soil texture maps where available. We tested national soil maps for Denmark (10 m × 10m; 30 × 30 m), Lithuania (100 × 100 m), and The Netherlands (25 ×x 25 m). However, open-access national digital soil maps (rasters) were not available for Northern Ireland and Turkey.

No_input: In this scenario, no coarse-resolution map was used as input for *soilscaler* model. In this case, the model used only the sensor information and soil samples from other sites to predict one of the sites in each interaction. We tested this scenario for all cases.

DSM: In this scenario, we applied the conventional DSM approach, mapping each field individually using its own sensor information and soil samples. This scenario aims to represent the best prediction and should work as a reference map for the spatial evaluation of other downscaling scenarios. We tested this scenario for all cases. Our hypothesis is that a successful downscaling process should display outputs with similar trends to the DSM outputs.

2.4. Proximal and remote sensing images

In all fields, we collected satellite and aerial/UAV remote sensing images, and proximal sensor data from electromagnetic induction (EMI) instruments to test the downscaling process. Figure 2 represents an examples of the bands of remote and proximal sensors used for downscaling in the Vindum field in Denmark.

The satellite images were obtained through Google Earth Engine (<https://earthengine.google.com/>). We downloaded bare soil images from the Copernicus Sentinel-level 2A and created a mosaic with images from January 2019 to May 2024 for each study site. Level 2A images also contain a mask for cloud/snow that helped to select only bare soil images. For bare soil aerial images, we used 2 - 4 bare soil RGB orthophotos from the Danish fields from flights (piloted airplane) in the years 2006 to 2018 (Agency for Data Supply and Efficiency, 2019). In Northern Ireland, the soil was not bare during the project period, and we were unable to use bare soil imagery from UAV. Instead, we relied on the NDRE index. For the other countries, UAV surveys were conducted under bare soil conditions (either on the same day as the soil sampling or shortly after), and Hyperspectral data was also collected in the fields in The Netherlands.

In Denmark, we used EC_a measurements from EMI surveys conducted with a DUALEM-21S sensor (Dualem Inc., Milton, ON, Canada) between 2010 to 2012 across five fields. In Lithuania, EC_a data were collected in 2021 using the DUALEM-21H sensor (Dualem Inc., Milton, ON, Canada) across five agricultural fields. In Northern Ireland and the Netherlands, we used EM38-MK2 and EM38 sensors, respectively. In Turkey, the EMI data was not available.

Fig. 1. Examples of aerial red band images (top), satellite images for bare soil (Sentinel band 3) (middle) and ECa measurements from an EMI instrument (bottom) from two fields in Denmark.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of downscaling varied according to the local conditions and the applied method. Here we present each study case (Country) separately, and we investigate the potential of using individual sensors and fusion sensor for improving the downscaling approach.

3.1. Aerial images for downscaling

Soil Organic Carbon

In Denmark, the downscaling process using coarse-resolution maps consistently show higher CCC values at Estrup and Vindum compared to other fields, which is also visible in the resulting downscaled maps (Fig. 3; Fig.S1). At Vindum, DSM demonstrates the best performance, achieving an RMSE of 0.65% compared with NULL_RMSE of 2.18%, a high CCC of 0.96, and an observed median of 2.2%, closely matched by the predicted median of 2.18%. Comparatively, predictions based on SoilGrids had the lowest performance, with an RMSE of 2.35%, CCC of 0.57, and a predicted median of 4.12%. National SOC maps for downscaling performed well for Vindum, with National10 achieving an RMSE of 1.84%, CCC of 0.68, a predicted median of 2.59%, while National30 showed an RMSE of 2.14%, CCC of 0.61, and a predicted median of 1.62%. The absence of coarse resolution maps (No input) also performed well for Vindum and Estrup. We also observed that the national maps tend to underestimate the high SOC concentrations in Estrup (Fig. 3).

In Northern Ireland, DSM presented the best performance to predict SOC at Hill field, with an RMSE of 0.09% and a CCC of 0.74, while the NULL model RMSE was 0.26%, indicating DSM's significant advantage over the baseline (Fig. 3; Fig S2). The predicted median of 2.81% was the same as the observed median, demonstrating strong predictive accuracy. Comparatively, the downscaling approach without input map at Hill showed an RMSE of

1.79% and a CCC of 0.00, with a predicted median of 4.17%, performing worse than the NULL_RMSE of 0.26%. Similarly, SoilGrids at Hill delivers poor results, with an RMSE of 7.50% and a CCC of 0.01, also underperforming the NULL_RMSE. It is visible that using SoilGrids for downscaling overestimated the SOC values in these fields. Although the downscaling approaches were unable to achieve higher performance in the Northern Irish fields, the example at Brecart A, shows that the downscaling process decreases the uncertainty of the global maps and present results similar to the DSM model.

The prediction of SOC for the fields in Lithuania presented high performance using DSM, followed by National and No input models with higher values than predictions based on SoilGrids (Fig. 3, Fig. S3). DSM had the best performance at Rumokai, with an RMSE of 0.30% and a CCC of 0.57, and a NULL_RMSE of 0.41%. National model had an RMSE of 0.84% and a CCC of 0.12 at Rumokai. No input map performed similar with an RMSE of 0.51% and a CCC of 0.12. The Lyduokiai field, with a NULL_RMSE of 0.48%, presented similar performance comparing DSM, National and No input (CCC and RMSE around 0.25 and 0.43%, respectively), which can also be observed in the spatial distribution of SOC in the downscaled maps. Comparatively, predictions based on SoilGrids showed an RMSE of 3.03% and a CCC of 0.01 and overestimated the SOC values for this field.

In the Netherlands, the downscaling scenarios National, No input and SoilGrids inputs maps did not achieve similar performance to the DSM approach (Fig 3, Fig S4). The outputs using the three coarse resolution input maps were also quite similar. DSM provides the best performance for SOC at PlassteegZuidveld1, with an RMSE of 0.21%, a CCC of 0.73, with a NULL_RMSE of 0.25%. The predicted median, 5.15% was identical to the median, showing a high level of accuracy. Using the National map resulted in moderate performance at PlassteegZuidveld2, showing an RMSE of 0.67%, a CCC of 0.36, a NULL_RMSE of 0.48%, and a predicted median of 5.36%. No input model at PlassteegNoordveld shows weaker

performance, with an RMSE of 1.14%, a CCC of 0.07, a NULL_RMSE of 0.62%, and a predicted median of 3.76%. Predictions based on SoilGrids did not appear in the top performers for SOC. Although the downscaled maps for the Dutch sites presented higher resolution, the spatial distribution of the SOC is very uncertain, and we the field average values seems the best to be used in this case. This can be related to the small variation of SOC and low soil and landscape variability in this field.

In the Turkish fields, all models did not perform well for the prediction of SOC (Fig 3; Fig S5), with only Karatay present a CCC values over 0.2 for DSM model. Karatay presented the best performance with an RMSE of 0.18 (compared to a NULL_RMSE of 0.19), a CCC of 0.27. No input model at Karatay showed an RMSE of 0.28 (compared to a NULL_RMSE of 0.19), and a CCC of 0.08. SoilGrids at Kadinhani has an RMSE of 0.30 (compared to a NULL_RMSE of 0.23), a CCC of 0.03, an observed median of 1.58, and a predicted median of 1.81.

The use of aerial/UAV images for downscaling SOC showed high potential for producing maps at high resolution (~1 m resolution). Reasonable performance was achieved by sites in Denmark and Lithuania, and its main related to the SOC variability in the specific field and the differences between the field. For instance, the downscaling approaches at Vindum field presented high performance, and it is due to the high spatial variability of SOC and it is captured by the drone images. In addition, the use of aerial/UAV images helped to identify hotspots of SOC concentrations that were not visible in national maps (10 and 30 m). This represents a great possibility to improve the SOC accounting schemes and the management of these unique areas. The lower performance in UK is linked with the fact that we did not use bare soil images from the UAV. The soil was covered by straw during the entire study period (2021-2023) and we used the NDRE index instead. Drones have been used to map SOC at field level and it is due to the high correlation between SOC and spectral reflectance.

Figure 3. Maps of soil organic carbon (SOC) derived from aerial/UAV images using the *soilscaler* R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (*soilscaler*) and without input maps (No Input). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

Soil texture

In Denmark, DSM performed best at Estrup for predicting clay, achieving an RMSE of 0.92%, a CCC of 0.68, a predicted median of 12.83%, compared to an observed median of 12.04% (Fig 4; Fig S6). The NULL_RMSE for Estrup is 2.94%, confirming DSM's strong performance. National30 follows with an RMSE of 1.74% and a CCC of 0.17, still lower than the NULL_RMSE, but showing weaker predictive power compared to DSM. National10 performed poorly with an RMSE of 3.57% and a CCC of 0.05%, while predictions based on SoilGrids achieved the lowest accuracy, with an RMSE of 4.31% and a CCC of 0.03. At Faardrup, DSM showed weaker results for clay, with an RMSE of 1.33% and a negative CCC of -0.32, though still better than SoilGrids, which performs worst with an RMSE of 4.31%, well above its NULL_RMSE.

In Northern Ireland, the DSM model also performed the best at Hill, achieving an RMSE of 0.65% and a CCC of 0.69, better than the NULL_RMSE of 1.20% (Fig 4; Fig S7). No input at Barn follows with an RMSE of 2.54% and a CCC of 0.17, while the NULL_RMSE for Barn is 2.58%, indicating a performance close to the baseline. Predictions based on SoilGrids at Barn shows the lowest accuracy, with an RMSE of 11.24% and a CCC of 0.01, compared to the NULL_RMSE of 2.58%, showing poor predictive power with a predicted median of 19.72%. At Brecart A, DSM also presented good results with an RMSE of 2.49% and a CCC of 0.61, outperforming the NULL_RMSE of 6.67%. Maps produced without an input map at Brecart A performed much worse, with an RMSE of 6.86% and a CCC of 0.09, while using SoilGrids as inputs gave a low accuracy with an RMSE of 8.94% and a CCC of 0.05.

In Lithuania, the best results for the Vievininkai field using National map as input (CCC = 0.47 and RMSE = 4.18%), and outperforms the DSM approach (Fig 4; Fig S8). This field also achieved higher accuracy for clay predictions without input map and with SoilGrids as the input map.

In The Netherlands, DSM presented the best performance for clay at PlassteegZuidveld2, achieving an RMSE of 0.49%, a CCC of 0.53, with a NULL_RMSE of 0.41% (Fig 4; Fig S9). National performed better at PlassteegZuidveld2 between the downscaling models, with an RMSE of 0.67%, a CCC of 0.36, a NULL_RMSE of 0.48%, and a predicted median of 5.36%, but the with RMSE still higher than the NULL_RMSE. In PlassteegNoordveld, predictions without an input map performed poorly with an RMSE of 1.14%, a CCC of 0.07, with a NULL_RMSE of 0.62%, while using SoilGrids as the input map have the lowest accuracy, with an RMSE of 17.52%, a CCC of 0.00, and a NULL_RMSE of 0.96%.

In Turkey, the models presented also poor performance for predicting clay (Fig S10), which had the best results from DSM at Karapinar, with an RMSE of 4.44 (compared to a NULL_RMSE of 4.73), and a CCC of 0.28. The model with no input map at Karatay performed poorly with an RMSE of 8.03 (compared to a NULL_RMSE of 7.32), and a CCC of -0.01. The model using SoilGrids at Cihanbeyli had the weakest performance with an RMSE of 9.96 (compared to a NULL_RMSE of 8.27) and a CCC of 0.00.

Figure 4. Maps of clay content derived from aerial/UAV images using the *soilscaler* R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (*soilscaler*) and without input maps (Extrapolation). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each

field without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

3.2. Satellite images for downscaling

Soil organic carbon

In Denmark, all models presented high prediction performance for SOC for Vindum and Estrup and it is visible in the similarity between the downscaled maps in Fig 5; Fig S11. The best performance for SOC prediction was observed with DSM at Vindum, with an RMSE of 1.28% and a high CCC of 0.90 with NULL_RMSE of 3.49%. Comparatively, predictions based on SoilGrids gave an RMSE of 2.53% and a CCC of 0.46. National10 has an RMSE of 2.67% and a CCC of 0.43. At Estrup, all models presented CCC values higher than 0.60. predictions based on SoilGrids delivers the best performance with an RMSE of 1.52% and a CCC of 0.82 with NULL_RMSE of 2.94. National30 at Estrup had an RMSE of 2.58% and a CCC of 0.63.

In Northern Ireland, none of the SOC downscaling models based on satellite images performed well, and the CCC values were around zero. However, the DSM approach achieved higher performance (Fig 5; Fig S12). DSM had the best performance at Brecart A, with an RMSE of 0.39% and a CCC of 0.92. The NULL_RMSE for Brecart A is 1.31%, indicating that DSM significantly outperforms the baseline. Comparatively, predictions without an input map at Brecart A showed an RMSE of 2.45% and a CCC of 0.04. At Barn, No input map performs worse with an RMSE of 3.00 and a CCC of 0.02, while the NULL_RMSE for Barn is 0.28%, indicating a significant underperformance. The visual analysis of downscaled maps also shows that predictions without inputs maps and SoilGrids predictions do not represent the spatial variability of SOC in these fields (Fig S12). The use of SoilGrids as mean values overestimated the SOC values for all fields.

In Lithuania, the DSM had the best performance at Rumokai, with an RMSE of 0.28% and a CCC of 0.48, with the NULL_model RMSE of 0.32%, meaning DSM slightly outperforms the baseline (Fig S13). For Lyduokiai, DSM achieved CCC of 0.58, but the RMSE of 0.35% is higher than the NULL_RMSE of 0.47%. Comparatively, predictions based on SoilGrids shows an RMSE of 2.63% and a CCC of 0.01 for Rumokai. The National model did not perform well compared to DSM and Predictions based on SoilGrids at Rumokai, with an RMSE of 0.80% and a CCC of 0.10, NULL_model RMSE of 0.41%. However, National predictions presented similar or lower RMSE for Lyduokiai (Fig 5) and Vėžaičiai compared with their NULL_RMSE.

In The Netherlands, the DSM approach presented the best performance, and the use of both Sentinel-2 images and hyperspectral data on the downscaling approaches tended to overestimate the SOC values for all fields (Fig S14; 15). In general, the PlassteegNoord field performed better than the PlassteegZuid fields, although the performance varied per method applied. In most cases, the patterns per field were similar for different methods, giving some confidence in the ability of satellite data to spatialize SOC data on such small fields with relatively small differences in SOC content. Of course, the resolution and reliability of the maps varies per input source and method and its suitability for application in a land management context should be evaluated depending on the foreseen management decisions and their impacts. When comparing the results between Satellite and Hyperspec covariates at PlassteegNoordveld, Hyperspec showed consistently slight better performance for SOC prediction. Hyperspec achieved a CCC of 0.87, with an RMSE of 0.33% and a NULL_RMSE of 0.74%. In comparison, the Satellite covariate for PlassteegNoordveld achieved a CCC of 0.78, an RMSE of 0.31%. While Satellite demonstrates relatively good performance, Hyperspec's lower RMSE values relative to the same NULL_RMSE indicate that Hyperspec offers more accurate SOC predictions at this location. Considering the downscaling models,

National presented better results than predictions based on SoilGrids (Fig 5.10; 5.11;5.12) and the downscaled maps using the hyperspectral images are more similar to the DSM maps.

In turkey, the DSM approach for predicting SOC distribution performed well only at Cihanbeyli, with lower performances at Karapinar and Karatay (Fig S16). The DSM model at Cihanbeyli resulted in a RMSE of 0.05, a CCC of 0.81, with a NULL_RMSE baseline of 0.12. The model without input map at Karatay performed slightly worse than the baseline, with an RMSE of 0.25, a CCC of 0.24, with a NULL_RMSE of 0.19. SoilGrids at Cihanbeyli had the lowest performance, with an RMSE of 0.85, a CCC of 0.01.

Figure 5. Maps of soil organic carbon (SOC) derived from Satellite images using the *soilscaler* R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (*soilscaler*) and without input maps (No Input). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

Soil Texture

The downscaling models based on satellite images were not able to predict the clay distribution for any fields in Denmark, but the error is still smaller for some fields when compared with the NULL_Model (Fig 6, Fig S17). Considering the DSM approach, the best performance was observed at Silstrup, where it achieves an RMSE of 0.77% and a CCC of 0.65 with NULL_RMSE of 1.21%, confirming that DSM performs moderately well. Comparatively, National_10m shows an RMSE of 1.68%, a CCC of -0.05. Among the downscaling models, the highest performance for clay was achieved by National30, which presented CCC value of 0.22 and RMSE of 1.66% with NULL_RMSE of 1.21%.

The predictions of soil texture in Northern Ireland followed the same trend as SOC, with higher values for DSM and lower for downscaling models (Fig S18). DSM had the best performance for clay at Brecart A, achieving an RMSE of 2.40 and a CCC of 0.89. The NULL_RMSE for Brecart A is 6.67, showing that DSM provides a much better prediction than the null model. The same is observed for Brecart B and Hill. However, No input at Hill shows an RMSE of 3.78 and a CCC of -0.08, which underperforms relative to the null model.

In Lithuania, DSM performs best at Lyduokiai, where it achieved an RMSE of 2.07% and a CCC of 0.62, and outperformed the NULL_RMSE of 2.72% (Fig S19). The National model followed with an RMSE of 2.90% and a CCC of 0.19. Predictions based on SoilGrids performed worse with an RMSE of 5.00% and a CCC of 0.08. The worst performance for clay is observed at Rumokai and Vėžaičiai for DSM and downscaling models.

In The Netherlands, DSM consistently provided the best performance across the different input maps (Fig S20; S21). The highest CCC value is achieved with the DSM method at PlassteegNoordveld using Hyperspec data, where the CCC reaches 0.87, with an RMSE of 0.42% and a NULL_RMSE of 0.74%. This is followed by another DSM result using satellite

images at PlassteegNoordveld, where the CCC is 0.76 with an RMSE of 0.49%. However, the downscaling approaches did not follow this trend, and the National, No input and SoilGrids models presented CCC values around zero. Although Satellite demonstrates relatively solid performance, Hyperspec's lower RMSE values, relative to the same NULL_RMSE, suggest that Hyperspec offers a more accurate prediction for clay.

In Turkey, the DSM approach for predicting clay distribution performed well only at Cihanbeyli and Karapinar, with lower performances at the other sites (Fig S22). The prediction of sand had lower performance in all models. The best performance for clay was achieved by DSM at Karapinar, with an RMSE of 3.22, a CCC of 0.65, and a NULL_RMSE of 0.13. No input map at Karapinar performs worse, with an RMSE of 7.79, a CCC of 0.06.

In general, the downscaled models using satellite images did not provide a good performance for predicting clay content. The issue here is also about variability. A few sites show high intra field variability in clay content and the correlation with the satellite images.

Figure 6. Maps of clay content derived from Satellite images using the soilscaler R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (soilscaler) and without input maps (No input). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

3.3. Electromagnetic induction measurements for downscaling

Soil Organic Carbon

In Denmark, downscaling models based on EMI were not able to identify patterns in SOC in the Danish fields (Fig 7; S23). The absence of correlation between EMI and SOC is evident for the fact that even the DSM model also did not achieve reasonable performance.

In Northern Ireland, the DSM model performed well for SOC mapping in almost all sites, except for Barn (Fig S24). On the other hand, the downscaling models without input maps and with SoilGrids as the input map had near zero values for CCC for predicting SOC, except for Barn. DSM had the best performance at at Brecart A, with an RMSE of 0.46%, a CCC of 0.90, and NULL_RMSE of 1.32% (Fig 7). Comparatively, predictions without input maps at Brecart A showed an RMSE of 2.42 and a CCC of 0.21, while predictions based on SoilGrids had lower performance with an RMSE of 6.42 and a CCC of -0.04. The SoilGrids maps overestimated the values of SOC for all fields (Fig 7).

In Lithuania, the models were not able to identify the spatial distribution of SOC in the fields, and only the DSM model for Vievininkai achieved CCC value higher than 0.3 (Fig S25). The DSM at Vievininkai had an RMSE of 0.28% and a CCC of 0.37, with the NULL_RMSE of 0.33%. DSM performed similar for Rumokai with an RMSE of 0.38%, CCC of 0.25, and a NULL_RMSE of 0.32%. The downscaling models were not able to find a similar pattern and had CCC values near zero.

In The Netherlands, the prediction of SOC followed the same pattern than the sites from Northern Ireland, where the downscaling approaches did not perform well for no one field (Fig S26). For instance, DSM had the best performance at PlassteegNoordveld, with an RMSE of

0.27%, a CCC of 0.83, and a NULL_RMSE of 0.74%. In the same field, National had an RMSE of 1.05%, a CCC of 0.02.

Figure 7. Maps of soil organic carbon (SOC) derived from EMI images using the *soilscaler* R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (*soilscaler*) and without input maps (No Input). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each

field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

Soil Texture

In Denmark, the performance of the EMI sensor for downscaling clay maps was higher compared to its accuracy for mapping SOC, especially using the National10 and 30 maps (Fig S27). Considering lower error, DSM performs best for clay prediction at Vindum and Silstrup. At Silstrup, DSM achieved an RMSE of 1.09% and a CCC of 0.64, with a NULL_RMSE of 1.53%. Considering the downscaling models, National10 had higher performance for Silstrup with an RMSE of 1.44% and a CCC of 0.40. Predictions based on SoilGrids had the lowest performance with an RMSE of 2.43% and a CCC of 0.19.

In Northern Ireland, DSM also provided the best performance at Brecart A (Fig 8; Fig S28), achieving an RMSE of 2.81% and a CCC of 0.86 with NULL_RMSE of 6.54%. DSM also presented higher performance for Brecart B and Hill. All downscaling models failed to predict clay with near zero CCC values and higher RMSE. The SoilGrids maps underestimated the clay values for all fields (Fig S28).

In Lithuania, the downscaling approach using the EMI sensor achieved higher performance for clay than for SOC (Fig S25; S29). The downscaling model using the National map outperformed the DSM approach and had the best value at Lyduokiai, with an RMSE of 2.39, a CCC of 0.62, with NULL_RMSE of 2.73. DSM at Vievininkai showed slightly lower performance, with an RMSE of 2.69 and a CCC of 0.56, and a NULL_RMSE of 3.63. The National model also performed well for Vievininkai where the RMSE was 3.64 and the CCC is 0.43, with NULL_model RMSE for Vievininkai is 3.71. No input and predictions based on SoilGrids also presented higher performance for the Vievininkai and Lyduokiai sites.

In The Netherlands, the downscaling models using EMI were also not able to predict the clay contents, but the DSM models performed reasonably well (Fig S30). DSM had the best performance for clay at PlassteegNoordveld, achieving an RMSE of 0.29%, a CCC of 0.90, and a NULL_RMSE of 0.96%. For comparison, the National model shows very low performance, with an RMSE of 2.08%, a CCC of -0.05. Although this RMSE is higher than the value for DSM, it performs better when compared with SoilGrids (RMSE = 20.95%). No input scenario at PlassteegNoordveld performed better than predictions based on SoilGrids, with an RMSE of 1.39%, a CCC of -0.05. The differences between input maps are visible in the maps, with National and predictions without input maps presenting more similar values compared with DSM than predictions based on SoilGrids (Fig 8; S30).

Figure 8. Maps of clay content derived from EMI images using the soilscaler R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (soilscaler) and without input maps (No Input). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

3.4. Individual sensors versus Sensor Fusion

Denmark

In general, applying the sensor-fusion approach did not improve SOC prediction performance based on CCC and RMSE metrics (Fig 9; Fig S31). The results were similar to using only aerial/UAV or satellite images, while EMI-based predictions had the lowest performance across all fields. Within the sensor-fusion approach, the best results were observed in the Vindum and Estrup fields using the DSM approach. For downscaling, predictions based on National10 soil maps and those without input maps performed similarly to the DSM approach, producing comparable maps. Comparing sensor performance for the same field, aerial images generally yielded higher accuracies, and sensor fusion added little, particularly at Vindum and Estrup.

For clay predictions, the sensor-fusion approach outperformed aerial and satellite images but was comparable to EMI-based results (Fig 9; Fig S36). Only Estrup and Vindum showed improvements with sensor fusion over EMI. Satellite images had the lowest performance among downscaling approaches for clay. Using DSM as a reference, sensor fusion achieved the best CCC values for Vindum, Silstrup, and Estrup, while Faardrup showed the lowest performance. National10, SoilGrids, and no input maps performed similarly, though National10 had the lowest RMSE, close to the DSM approach. Higher RMSE values for Estrup might be due to its large clay content variability.

Figure 9. Downscaling accuracy indexes using coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids, and without input maps (No input) for soil organic carbon (SOC) and clay for five fields in Denmark. . DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (CCC); Root Mean Square error (RMSE).

Northern Ireland (UK)

All the downscaling models produced very low performance results compared to the DSM results (Fig 10; Fig S32). Only the model without input maps for BrecartA presented CCC value higher than 0.1. The DSM approach had higher values for all models. Considering the RMSE, all models presented higher values when using the SoilGrids as input maps with almost 3-fold higher than using predictions without input maps. Sensor Fusion consistently delivered the best performance compared to other covariates like EMI, UAV, and Satellite (Sat_10m). At Brecart A, DSM using Sensor fusion achieved an RMSE of 0.46% and a CCC of 0.90, significantly outperforming the NULL_RMSE of 1.32%. In comparison, using SoilGrids at Brecart A under the same Sensor fusion covariate results in a much weaker RMSE of 6.31% and a CCC of -0.06, failing to surpass the baseline.

Regarding the clay predictions, the performance of Sensor Fusion was similar to the EMI and Satellite approaches (Fig 10; Fig S37). Amongst the approaches using Sensor fusion for mapping clay, DSM delivers the best performance at Brecart A, with an RMSE of 2.81% and a CCC of 0.86, compared to the NULL_RMSE of 6.54%. At Hill, DSM performs similarly well, with an RMSE of 0.43% and a CCC of 0.74, far outperforming the NULL_RMSE of 1.20%. However, the performance of Sensor fusion varies depending on the input map. For instance, at Barn, using SoilGrids results in an RMSE of 10.31% and a CCC of 0.03, while the NULL_RMSE for Barn is 2.58%, showing a clear underperformance relative to the baseline. Similarly, at Brecart B, predictions based on SoilGrids produces an RMSE of 22.45% and a CCC of 0.00, compared to the NULL_RMSE of 3.92%, indicating that DSM performs better than other input maps within Sensor fusion for mapping clay.

Figure 10. Downscaling accuracy indexes using coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids, and without input maps (No input) for soil organic carbon (SOC) and clay for four fields in North Ireland. DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (CCC); Root Mean Square error (RMSE).

Lithuania

Sensor Fusion results for SOC prediction showed performance similar to UAV and satellite images, while EMI sensors presented the lowest performance (Fig 11; Fig S33). Fields like Lyduokiai and Rumokai improved with Sensor Fusion within DSM. Among Sensor Fusion models, DSM reference performed best, followed by National map-based models and predictions without input maps, with variations across fields. For example, predictions without input maps performed better for Vėžaičiai, while National maps outperformed others for Vievininkai. SoilGrids consistently showed the lowest performance in CCC and RMSE among downscaling approaches. Most fields exhibited similar performance across sensors, but satellite image-based models produced the best results for Vėžaičiai and Vievininkai.

For clay content, Sensor Fusion appeared similar to EMI and looked better than satellite images, with notable differences for Lyduokiai and Vievininkai (Fig S38). Drone images produced the lowest performance overall. Within Sensor Fusion, National maps delivered the best performance for Lyduokiai and, together with SoilGrids-based predictions, represented good performance. Extrapolation generally did not result in strong performance, except for Vievininkai. At Lyduokiai, DSM within Sensor Fusion performed best, with an RMSE of 1.94% and a CCC of 0.63, outperforming the NULL_model RMSE of 2.72%. Predictions based on the National map followed, with an RMSE of 2.34% and a CCC of 0.5. Predictions without input maps showed an RMSE of 4.65% and a CCC of 0.19. SoilGrids-based predictions performed worst, with an RMSE of 4.87% and a CCC of 0.19, exceeding the NULL_model RMSE of 2.72%. National downscaled maps in Fig 7.6 represented spatial trends and showed values close to DSM maps, especially for Lyduokiai and Vievininkai, though SoilGrids consistently overestimated SOC values.

Figure 11. Downscaling accuracy indexes using coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids, National maps at 100m (National), and without input maps (No input) for soil organic carbon (SOC), clay and sand for four fields in Lithuania. DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (CCC); Root Mean Square error (RMSE).

The Netherlands

All the models presented similar results, with the use of hyperspectral images having slightly higher accuracies for the fields considering the models based on the National map and without input maps (Fig 12; Fig S34). The DSM model provided the best performance for SOC across various covariates, and it is the reference for the spatial distribution of SOC. While all covariates perform well, Hyperspectral and Satellite images outperformed EMI, especially at PlassteegNoordveld. Amongst the Sensor Fusion models, DSM at PlassteegNoordveld delivered the best performance, with a CCC of 0.84, an RMSE of 0.26%, with a NULL_RMSE of 0.44%. In the same field, the National model showed lower performance, with a CCC of 0.06, an RMSE of 0.95%. On the other hand, predictions without input maps performed worse at PlassteegNoordveld, with a CCC of 0.08 and an RMSE of 1.13%. Lastly, predictions based on SoilGrids showed the weakest performance, with a CCC value near 0, a high RMSE of 4.04%. These differences are clear when analysing the downscaled maps in Fig S.

For clay, Sensor Fusion presented similar results compared with using only the EMI covariate (Fig 12; Fig S39). The DSM models provided the best performance across various covariates. Among the different covariates, Sensor fusion and EMI using the DSM input map at PlassteegNoordveld delivered the highest performances (CCC = 0.90, RMSE = 0.29%), but Sensor Fusion provided a lower RMSE (0.24%) with NULL_RMSE of 0.81%. With the Sensor fusion, DSM at PlassteegNoordveld provides the best performance, and prediction based on the National map presented CCC of -0.09 and RMSE of 1.93%. Predictions based on SoilGrids performed worse with CCC of 0.00 and RMSE of 21.7%. Although the downscaling approaches using national map and predictions without input maps had lower performance values, the field mean values are similar to DSM output and do not overestimate the values as the outputs from SoilGrids (Fig 16).

Figure 13. Downscaling accuracy indexes using coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids, National maps at 25m (National) and without input maps (No input) for soil organic carbon (SOC) and Clay for three fields in The Netherlands. DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (CCC); Root Mean Square error (RMSE).

Turkey

Soil organic carbon

For Turkey, DSM showed lower performance for SOC and clay compared to fields in other countries, using aerial, satellite, or Sensor Fusion images (Fig 14; Fig S35). Only the DSM model for Cihanbeyli achieved a CCC above 0.5 with satellite and fusion data. SoilGrids consistently produced the highest prediction errors. Among covariates, the Satellite covariate using the DSM input map performed best for SOC, with an RMSE of 0.05 and a CCC of 0.81 at Cihanbeyli (NULL_RMSE = 0.12). Sensor Fusion with DSM followed, slightly lower at RMSE 0.06 and CCC 0.77. At Karatay, the Drone covariate with DSM performed poorly, with an RMSE of 0.18 and CCC of 0.27, although better than the NULL_RMSE of 0.20. Within Sensor Fusion, the "No input" model at Karatay performed worst, with an RMSE of 0.25 and CCC of 0.24, below the NULL_RMSE of 0.19. SoilGrids at Cihanbeyli had the weakest performance, with an RMSE of 0.85, CCC of 0.01, and NULL_RMSE of 0.12, significantly underperforming.

For clay, the Satellite covariate with DSM performed best, with an RMSE of 3.22 and a CCC of 0.65 (Fig 14; Fig S40), outperforming the NULL_RMSE of 4.92 at Karapinar. Sensor Fusion with DSM followed closely, with RMSE 3.32 and CCC 0.63. The aerial covariate with DSM performed worst at Karapinar, with RMSE 4.44 and CCC 0.28, though still better than the NULL_RMSE of 4.92. Within Sensor Fusion, the "No input" model at Karapinar performed poorly, with RMSE 5.84 and CCC 0.40. SoilGrids at Cihanbeyli had the weakest results, with RMSE 10.08, CCC 0.03, and NULL_RMSE 8.27, underperforming the baseline.

Figure 14. Downscaling accuracy indexes using coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids and without input maps (No input) for soil organic carbon (SOC) and Clay for four fields in Turkey. DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field without the downscaling process. Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (CCC); Root Mean Square error (RMSE).

Figure 15. Maps of soil organic carbon (SOC) derived from Sensor Fusion process using the *soilscaler* R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (*soilscaler*) and without input maps (No Input). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

Figure 16. Maps of clay content derived from Sensor Fusion process using the *soilscaler* R package with coarse resolution inputs maps from SoilGrids/National (*soilscaler*) and without input maps (No Input). DSM represents the results using the Digital Soil Mapping techniques for each field, based on local soil samples, without the downscaling process. SoilGrids/National represent the SOC maps available at coarse resolution.

4. Considerations and future research

In this study, we developed a framework to downscale coarse resolution maps to field-level high resolution maps and tested it across different regions in Europe using remote and proximal sensing, as well sensor fusion. We found that the performance of the downscaling process is intrinsically related to the local conditions and availability of reasonably accurate coarse resolution soil maps. In Denmark, where five fields with different soil properties and variation and national maps at 10 m resolution area available, the models presented the best performance. In contrast, the use of SoilGrids as coarse resolution input maps did not result in representative soil maps, as the downscaling approach tended to use the global mean values and overestimated the local values. In these cases, the use of predictions without input maps seemed to be the best option. This is the first attempt to downscale soil maps across different regions in Europe and we have indicated below our considerations regarding the main conclusions, gaps in the present knowledge and future applications of downscaled soil maps.

Main conclusions outputs

- In our analysis, Satellite and aerial sensors showed superior performance for SOC (Soil Organic Carbon) prediction, while EMI sensors were more effective for soil texture prediction.
- Generally, most downscaled models presented lower performance compared with the NULL model and local DSM model, but it is essential to note that no soil samples were used. Despite this, the downscaled soil maps better capture spatial variability and align more closely with DSM maps than national or global soil maps. This represents a significant improvement given the absence of soil samples.
- Soil variability, both within and between fields, is crucial for achieving high performance. Across all countries, better results were observed in fields with greater

soil variability, as seen in Denmark and Lithuania. Conversely, fields with lower variability, such as those in the Netherlands, showed poorer performance, even with the DSM approach using local samples.

Research Gaps and Future Directions

Our tests of different sensors across varying local contexts have highlighted key areas for improvement in downscaling methods for soil maps.

- When collecting UAV images, it is crucial to ensure bare soil conditions across all fields. Fields without bare soil conditions, like those in Northern Ireland, showed poor results, as mixed conditions (bare soil and vegetated areas) hinder the downscaling process. This is essential for SOC predictions.
- Field selection should prioritize spatial variability in soil texture and SOC concentration. A wide range of soil variability enhances the model's ability to predict soil properties for new unsampled fields.
- Soil sensors show significant potential, and future research should focus on building databases that integrate soil samples with remote and proximal sensors. Spectroscopy databases, which now predict various soil properties at low cost, is an example of such a successful initiative. Similar databases for proximal and remote sensing data could greatly improve the potential for downscaling soil maps across the world.
- Developing higher resolution national and regional soil maps will be necessary to reduce uncertainty in downscaling. Global maps introduce substantial uncertainty, but high-resolution national maps can mitigate this effect.
- In this study, we only aimed to test the effect of using individual sensors and sensor fusion. Future studies should also add other local environmental variables that may help to map the spatial distribution of soil properties. For instance, the covariates derived

from Digital Elevation Models can be relevant information for predicting the spatial distribution of soil properties in fields with landscape variation.

Downscaled soil maps can offer a valuable source of information for sustainable soil management when soil samples are not available. While these maps are not a final solution, like any other digital soil map, they serve as a foundational and first tool for analysing soil property distributions in geographic space. Our findings indicate that downscaled sensor-based soil maps outperform existing national and global products in estimating SOC and clay contents. National soil maps, despite their high resolution (approximately 10 m in the Danish case), often lack essential covariates needed to assess soil variability within individual fields. This limitation is especially critical for applications involving local soil management practices, carbon accounting, environmental regulations, or taxation, where more precise soil variability assessments are necessary for accuracy and compliance.

In conclusion, the downscaling approach tested in this study across various countries and climates in Europe underscores the potential of remote and proximal sensors in refining coarse-resolution maps to field-level detail. As more researchers adopt sensor-based mapping, further enhancements are expected. We anticipate that the *soilscaler* package will gain widespread use and that increased access to soil samples and sensor data will continue to improve predictive accuracy in soil management practices.

Acknowledgements

This research was developed in the framework of the European Joint Program for SOIL “Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils” (EJP SOIL) funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement N° 862695) and by the participating Member States.

Author contributions

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